

THESIS OF THE RESEARCH WORK ON TOPIC: PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF SUPERVISION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING IN PREPARING THE DEFECTOLOGIES OF THE FUTURE

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Annotation: Thesis shows the dependence of research and the purpose of the study, object of research, subject of research, upcoming scientific news.

Key words: Proposals, development, technology, effective teaching, pathologists.

Dependence of research on the main priorities of the development of science and technology of the republic. This dissertation was implemented in the framework of the priority direction of the development of science and technology of the republic I. "Spiritual, moral and cultural development of a democratic and legal society, the formation of an innovative economy."

The purpose of the study: to develop proposals and recommendations for improving the mechanisms of effective teaching of English in the training of future speech pathologists.

Object of research: the process of teaching English in the training of future defectologists.

Subject of research: pedagogical conditions, content, form, method and means of teaching English in the training of future defectologists.

Upcoming scientific news:

- Pedagogical conditions for effective teaching of English in the training of future defectologists will be developed on the basis of modern approaches;
- Improving the mechanisms of effective teaching of English in the training of future speech pathologists, reflecting the integration of goals, principles, content, forms, methods, tools, stages, criteria and results;
- Mechanisms to ensure the effectiveness of English language teaching will be improved on the basis of components of educational activities, innovative activities and technological support of educational activities;
- Criteria and methods for assessing the quality of teaching English in the training of future speech pathologists will be developed on the basis of the principles of systematicity, diversity, completeness, consistency, fairness, authenticity, authenticity.

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